

TISSUE ENGINEERING IN REGENERATIVE ENDODONTICS -A REVIEW

*JANAVATHI¹, SHARDHA BAI RATHOD², NAVEEN KUMAR M³, RAMADEVI⁴

¹Senior Lecturer, Dept. of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics, ³Reader, Dept. of Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology, Sree Sai Dental College and Research Institute, Srikakulam, Andhra Pradesh. ²Senior resident, BLDE University's Shri B.M. Patil Medical College and Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapur, Karnataka. ⁴Associate professor, Dept. of Pathology, Shantaram Medical College, Nandyal, Kurnool, Andhra Pradesh, India.

*Corresponding author email: jandr@rediffmail.com

Received: 07th Jan 2015, Accepted: 10th Mar 2015.

ABSTRACT

Tissue engineering is mainly used to replace the impaired or damaged tissues with new tissues. The key cells involved for tissue engineering are stem cells, the morphogens or growth factors. They will rapidly multiply and differentiates and forms tissues. This new technique is now most commonly used in endodontics. The aim of this study was to review about the dental pulp stem cells, which are most common growth factors, and the scaffolds used to control their differentiation. To study the clinical technique for the management of immature non-vital teeth based on this novel concept.

KEYWORDS: Dental pulp stem cells, morphogens, scaffolds, regenerative endodontics, pulp revascularization.

INTRODUCTION

Now a day's root canal treatment has high level of success for several conditions. The main concept in this treatment is regenerative approach. In which replace diseased or necrotic pulp tissues with healthy pulp tissues, mainly to revitalize teeth. This type of regenerative approach if we are using in endodontics it's called as regenerative endodontics. This method provides a new range of biologically based clinical treatments in endodontic diseases.

Tissue Engineering

Tissue engineering is a rapidly developing field. It has the principle of engineering and life science. These principles are mainly applied for, the development of biological substitutes which can restore, maintain or improve functioning of tissue. The major elements involved for tissue engineering are stem cells, morphogens or growth factors, and an extracellular matrix scaffold. The chief tissues required for regenerative endodontics are dentin, pulp, cementum and periodontal tissues ^[1-3].

Key Elements for Tissue Engineering

Stem cells

These were considered to be the most important cells in regenerative medicine.

Research on stem cells provided knowledge about, the development of an organism from a single cell, and how healthy cells can replace damaged ones in adult organisms. Stem cells have the capacity for continuous division. Either for self-replication (replicate themselves), or multilineage differentiation (to produce specialized cells which can differentiate into various other types of cells or tissues) ^[4].

Types of stem cells

Early embryonic stem cells

The human development occurs with the division of newly fertilized egg or zygote. It produces a group of stem cells called an embryo. These early stem cells are called totipotent, which means these can be developed to any kind of cell in the body.

Blastocyst embryonic stem cells

After five days of fertilization, embryo develops a hollow ball-like structure which is known as blastocyst. The embryonic stem cells of the blastocyst are pluripotent, means they have the ability to become almost any kind of cell in the body. Researchers can induce these cells to create a specialized cells. But, this method is not yet fully developed. Mainly due to the source of embryonic stem cells which is controversial, and it's mainly associated with ethical and legal issues. This reduced the development of new therapies [5].

Fetal stem cells

8 weeks after development of embryo is known as a fetus. By this period a human-like form will be developed. Fetal stem cells were responsible for the initial development of all tissues before birth. Fetal stem cells were also pluripotent.

Umbilical cord stem cells

Fetus gets the nutrients and oxygen rich blood from placenta by umbilical cord. Umbilical cord blood contains stem cells, which are genetically similar with new born. Stem cells of umbilical cord are multipotent. They can be developed to a limited range of cell types. For the purpose of medical therapy umbilical cord stem cells can be stored cryogenically.

Adult stem cells

These stem should be called as post natal stem cells. Because, these cells are also present in infants and children. These cells mainly stay on tissues which are already developed, and they maintain the growth of these tissues throughout life.

These were also multipotent. Usually adult stem cells generate the same cell types, on which they are residing. Researchers had observed plasticity with these cells. It means that stem cells from one tissue may develop cells of different tissues^[6]. These particular stem cells were present on almost whole body tissues^[7], including dental tissues^[8, 9]. Till now, four types of human dental stem cells have been isolated and characterized: i) Dental pulp stem cells (DPSCs)^[10], ii) Stem cells from human exfoliated deciduous teeth (SHED)^[11], iii) Stem cells from apical

papillae (SCAP)^[12,13], and iv) Periodontal ligament stem cells (PDLSCs)^[14].

All these dental stem cell were developed from permanent teeth, except SHED. Identification of these stem cell provided a better knowledge, on the regenerative property of pulp and periodontal ligament tissues after tissue damage^[1].

Progenitor cells

Generally intermediate cells are known as precursor or progenitor cells. These progenitor cells are developed from stem cells. Before to the full differentiation of stem cells these cells were formed. These cells will be differentiated along a particular cellular development pathway. Till the stem cells get the property of multitissue differentiation and self renewal properties, they were considered as progenitor cells^[15].

Dental pulp stem cells (DPSCs)

Gronthos et al first isolated DPSCs in the year 2000. They have capacity to regenerate dentin pulp complex similar to regeneration caused by normal human teeth. Later, same group identified^[16], that these cells have a high proliferative capacity, a selfrenewal property and a multi-lineage differentiation potential. Scientists also isolated a selected subpopulation of DPSCs called as Stromal Bone-producing Dental Pulp Stem Cells (SBP-DPSCs). These are multipotential cells, they have the ability to give a variety of cell types and tissues. They are osteoblasts, adipocytes, myoblasts, endotheliocytes, and melanocytes, as well as neural cell progenitors (neurons and glia), being of neural crest origin^[17-21].

Several studies were conducted on DPSCs^[10, 16, 22-30]. These studies has shown that DPCs were multipotent stromal cells, they have extensive proliferative capacity, they can be safely cryopreserved, they have several scaffolds of applications, they posses long lifespan, immunosuppressive properties^[31], and they can form mineralized tissues which is similar to dentin^[32, 33].

Paakkonen et al. demonstrated that DPSCs got gene expression pattern which was similar to the mature native odontoblasts. This property can be helpful for in vitro studies of odontoblasts, that they can form a humanderived cell line.^[34] However, no

definite proof was established for their ability to produce a dentin. R Takeda et al. isolated the hDPSCs from tooth germs at the crown-completed stage. They had observed that these cells were highly proliferative and had the potential to generate a dentin-like matrix *in vivo*. [35]

These properties are not long lasting due to changes in gene expression profile. Abe et al. isolated apical pulp derived cells (APDCs) present on human teeth. They described that these cells has the capacity to regenerate even on hard tissues. [36]

SHED

These cells were first isolated by Miura et al. [11]. They observed that these cell have a greater capacity to regenerate to a variety of cells in comparison to DPSCs. They can regenerate to neural cells, adipocytes, osteoblast-like and odontoblast-like cells. The main function of these cells is to form mineralized tissue [18, 37, & 38]. This can be used for regeneration of orofacial bone [39].

Because of the ethical issues associated with the use of embryonic stem cells, and limited availability of autologous postnatal stem cells with multipotentiality, SHED has become an alternate source for dental tissue engineering [11]. Compared to the stem cells from adult human teeth, SHED was more helpful for tissue engineering. They got high proliferation rate than stem cells from permanent teeth [11]. They can also be retrieved from a tissue that is disposable and readily accessible [40]. They were suitable for young patients during mixed dentition, who were already suffered with pulp necrosis immature permanent teeth because of trauma. [41]

SCAP

Sonoyama et al discovered a new variety of population of mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs), which were residing on the apical papilla of permanent immature teeth. They were also known as stem cells from the apical papilla (SCAP) [13]. They reported that these cells express various mesenchymal stem cell markers. These cells has the capacity to form odontoblast-like cells, producing dentin *in vivo*. They were also primary source for odontoblasts formation on root dentin. It was observed that on the infected immature permanent teeth with periradicular periodontitis or abscess, apexogenesis may occur. It is mainly

due to the presence of SCAP on the apical papilla. It can survive during pulp necrosis, mainly because of its proximity to the vasculature of the periapical tissues. So, these cells has the capacity to generate primary odontoblast for complete root formation after the endodontic disinfection [13].

Periodontal ligament stem cells (PDLSCs)

Seo et al first described the presence of multipotent postnatal stem cells in the human PDL (PDLSCs). They used same methodology which was used for isolation of MSCs from deciduous and adult pulp for these cells also [42]. They described that PDLSCs can differentiated into cementoblast-like cells, adipocytes, and collagen-forming cells under definite cell cultures. In immunocompromised rodents, PDLSCs generated a cementum/PDL-like structure and promoted the healing of periodontal tissue repair. Trubiani et al also supported the presence of MSCs in the periodontal ligament [43]. They isolated and characterized a population of MSCs from the periodontal ligament which expressed a variety of stromal cell markers. Shi et al. [44], demonstrated that generation of cementum-like structures associated with PDL-like connective tissue after transplanting PDLSCs with hydroxyapatite/tricalcium phosphate particles to immunocompromised mice. These cells got several clinical applications, mainly because even after isolation from cryopreserved periodontal ligaments they maintained its stem cell properties. Which were the expression of MSC surface markers, multipotential differentiation, single-colony strain generation and cementum/periodontal-ligament-like tissue regeneration. These properties made them an instant source for MSCs [45]. By using a minipig model, autologous SCAP and PDLSCs were loaded onto hydroxyapatite/tricalcium phosphate and gelfoam scaffolds. Then they were implanted on sockets of the lower jaw, there they formed a bioroot encircled with periodontal ligament tissue in a natural relationship with the surrounding bone [46]. Trubiani et al. observed the regenerative property of PDLSCs when they were cultivated on a three-dimensional biocompatible scaffold. This property was useful in making of graft biomaterials, for bone tissue engineering in regenerative dentistry. [47] Li et al. Observed that, PDLSCs when seeded on bioengineering produced cementum and periodontal ligament-like tissue formation. [48]

Stem cells culturing

The growth and maintenance of cells in a controlled environment outside an organism was referred as cell culture. Ideal goals of stem cell culture are to keep the cells healthy, dividing, and unspecialized.

Dental pulp stem cells were mainly cultured by two methods; the first method is enzyme-digestion method [10,11,13,49]. In this, using sterile conditions pulp tissue was collected. Then it was digested with suitable enzymes. The formed cell suspensions were cultured on dishes with a special medium. They were provided with necessary additives and properly incubated. The resulting colonies were sub cultured before confluence and then cells were stimulated for differentiation.

The explants outgrowth method was the second method of isolation of dental pulp stem cells [50-53]. In this method, initially the extruded pulp tissues were cut into 2-mm³ cubes. Then they were anchored via microcarriers onto a suitable substrate, and they were directly incubated in culture dishes which contain the essential medium with supplements. It takes around 2 weeks of time for sufficient number of cells to grow and come out of the tissues. Haung et al. compared both these methods and concluded that, cells isolated by enzyme-digestion has high proliferation rate than isolated by outgrowth method. [54]

Stem cells differentiation

Cell differentiation is the process in which specialized cells were generated from unspecialized stem cells. It is mainly triggered by signals from both inside and outside of the cells. The internal signals were controlled by the genes of cells. The genetic information will be carried across DNA, leading generation of coded instructions for the structural maintenance and functioning of a cell. Whereas the external signals for cell differentiation may include several factors. Which were chemicals secreted by neighboring cells, physical contact with other cells and presence of certain molecules in the microenvironment. Depending upon the contents of media cultured dental pulp stem cells can be stimulated to differentiate to more than one cell type. Osteo/dentinogenic medium mainly contains dexamethasone, glycerophosphate, ascorbate phosphate and 1,25 dihydroxy vitamin D with other basic

elements [10]. Adipogenic medium contains dexamethasone, insulin and isobutyl methylxanthine [55]. For neurogenic induction of cells they were cultured in the presence of B27 supplement, basic fibroblast growth factor and epidermal growth factor. [11]

Cell lines

The first step involved in making cell lines is to cultivate the stem cells. For research and development purpose genetically identical cells should be collected and cultivated. After attaining a stable stem cell line, it can be stimulated to differentiate into specialized cell types. Generally odontoblasts cannot be induced for further differentiation, because they were postmitotic terminally differentiated cells. Odontoblast after their full differentiation produces various proteins. One is type I collagen, it forms the scaffold for mineral deposition and provides strength for mineralizing dentin. The two other major noncollagenous proteins (NCPs) had mineralization-regulatory capacities [56]. These proteins are dentin phosphophoryn (DPP; or DMP-2) and dentin sialoprotein (DSP)[57]. These two proteins were encoded by a single gene. The phenotypic characteristics of dentin were explained by DSPP or DMP-3[58-61]. One more important non collagenous protein is dentin matrix protein-1 (DMP-1). It was found primarily in dentin and bone. It mainly helps for regulating mineralization [62-64]. While DPSCs differentiation DMP-1 acts as a growth factor [65,66].

Odontoblast cell line is useful to explore the pulp wound-healing mechanism and also to develop therapeutic strategy for pulp regeneration. odontogenic differentiation was not fully understood mainly because of two limitations.

The first is the paucity of differentiation markers, it is now overcome by the characterization of odontoblastspecific markers (DMP-1, DMP-2, and DMP-3) that can indicate the presence of a true odontoblastic cell line [61, 67 & 68]. The second limitation is the limited life span of the primary cells [69]. It's been addressed by several methodological trials including cell cloning and immortalization [61,70-74].

Growth factors

Morphogenesis or organogenesis is mainly mediated by signals produced by growth factors. The specialization or division of stem cells to the required cell type was mainly regulated stem cells. They mediate several key cellular events during tissue regeneration, which includes cell proliferation, chemotaxis, differentiation, and matrix synthesis [75]. Growth factors are of two types, one type is quite versatile, and it stimulates cellular division in numerous cell types, while the other one is more cell-specific. Growth factors are used for various purposes. 1) Certain growth factors were mainly used to increase stem cell numbers. Likewise platelet-derived growth factor (PDGF), fibroblast growth factor (FGF) [76], insulin-like growth factor (IGF), colony-stimulating factor (CSF) and epidermal growth factor (EGF). 2) While few growth factors modifies the humoral and cellular immunity (interleukins 1- 13). 3) Whereas few growth factors regulate angiogenesis, e.g. vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) [77, 78]. Another e.g. for growth factor, transforming growth factor is helpful in wound healing and tissue regeneration/ engineering [75, 79, & 80]. 4) Growth factor such as bone morphogenic proteins (BMPs) was helpful in tooth development [81, 82] and regeneration [3].

Bone morphogenetic proteins (BMPs)

These are multi-functional growth factors, they belongs to the family of transforming growth factor [83]. The BMPs were first identified by their ability to form ectopic bone formation, while implanted under the skin of rodents [84]. Till now, around 20 BMP family members have been identified and characterized. They have unique biological activities *in vivo*, it's mainly because of their differences in profiles of expression, affinities for receptors binding [85]. BMPs play a major role in teeth formation. Their dictation leads to initiation, morphogenesis, cytodifferentiation, and matrix secretion will occur. BMP family of growth factors is important in forming the enamel knot of teeth. Without these BMPs there won't be teeth formation [86]. BMPs [87-90] and growth factors [91] together were used directly in capping pulp. This phenomenon of adding of growth factors to stem cells was helpful in tissue engineering and to replace the diseased tooth tissues.

BMPs are used for two types of therapies for dentin regeneration. The first is the *in vivo* therapy, in which BMPs or BMP genes are directly applied to the exposed or amputated pulp. The second is *ex vivo* therapy, first DPSCs was isolated. Further they will be differentiated to odontoblasts with recombinant BMPs or BMP genes. Last step is their autogenous transplantation to regenerate dentin [86]. BMP-2 plays a crucial role in dentin regeneration [92]. Recombinant human BMP-2 increases the odontoblast like stem cells by promoting the differentiation of adult pulp stem cells in culture [53, 93 & 94]. It promotes the expression of dentin sialophosphoprotein (DSPP) gene *in vitro* mainly by promoting their alkaline phosphatase activity. [53] It also increases the hard tissue formation *in vivo* [95]. Dentin formation can be promoted by autogenous transplantation of BMP-2-treated pellet culture onto amputated pulp [96]. Even BMP-7 also showed same findings. It also known as osteogenic protein-1. It promoted the reparative dentinogenesis and pulp mineralization in several animal models [97-103]. Lin et al. [104] generated a BMP-7-expressing adenoviral vector that induced the expression of BMP-7 in primarily cultured human dental pulp cells. This expression led to a significant increase of alkaline phosphatase activity and induced the expression of DSPP, suggesting that BMP-7 can promote the differentiation of human pulp cells into odontoblast-like cells and promote mineralization *in vitro*. However, a novel role has been suggested for BMP-4, which is secreted by mesenchymal cells, in the regulation of Hertwig's epithelial root sheath (HERS) during root development by preventing elongation and maintaining cellular proliferation. Therefore it has been utilized as an agent for regulating root formation in a variety of tissue engineering applications [105].

Scaffolds

Scaffolds are used to provide a physicochemical and biological three-dimensional microenvironment or tissue construct for cell growth and differentiation. It can be implanted singly or in combination with growth factors and stem cells. [66,106- 108]

Ideal requirements of a scaffold [66,109-112]

(a) Should be porous to allow placement of cells and growth factors.

- (b) Should allow effective transport of nutrients, oxygen, and waste.
- (c) Should be biodegradable, leaving no toxic byproducts.
- (d) Should be replaced by regenerative tissue while retaining the shape and form of the final tissue structure.
- (e) Should be biocompatible.
- (f) Should have adequate physical and mechanical strength.

Types of scaffold

a) Biological/natural scaffolds

These consist of natural polymers such as collagen and glycosaminoglycan. It offers good biocompatibility and bioactivity. The tensile strength of tissues is mainly increased by collagen. Collagen is present mainly on extracellular matrix. As a scaffold, collagen allows easy placement of cells and growth factors and allows replacement with natural tissues after undergoing degradation [113-115]. It is observed that pulp cells in collagen matrices undergo marked contraction, this might affect the pulp tissue regeneration [54,116].

b) Artificial scaffolds

These are synthetic polymers. They have controlled physicochemical features such as degradation rate, microstructure, and mechanical strength [112], for example:

- Polylactic acid (PLA), polyglycolic acid (PGA), and their copolymers, poly lactic-co-glycolic acid (PLGA).
- Synthetic hydrogels include polyethylene glycol (PEG)- based polymers.
- Scaffolds modified with cell surface adhesion peptides, such as arginine, glycine, and aspartic acid (RGD) to improve cell adhesion and matrix synthesis within the three-dimensional network [117].
- Scaffolds containing inorganic compounds such as hydroxyapatite (HA), tricalcium phosphate (TCP) and calcium polyphosphate (CPP), which are used

to enhance bone conductivity [118], and have proved to be very effective for tissue engineering of DPSCs [119,120].

- Micro-cavity-filled scaffolds to enhance cell adhesion [121,122].

Scaffolds for tissue engineering

Various researchers have showed that pulp cells can be isolated, multiplied in culture, and can be seeded onto a matrix scaffold. The new tissue formed by cultured cells was similar to that of the native pulp. [10, 22, 41, 66, 111, 123-127] These results were helpful to generate pulp and dentin in pulpless canals. Blood flow is necessary for vitality of the implanted cells. While implanting cells into root canals, vascularization should be increased. Because, they will have blood only from apical end. To promote the action, growth factors such as VEGF and/or platelet-derived growth factor or endothelial cells can be added. [46]

Tissue engineering concept: Clinical applications

Several clinical studies showed that teeth apexification can be treated with apexogenesis [128-137]. We can also use biological based treatment, it promotes dentin of the root as well root tip formation [138]. Iwaya et al. [137] and Banchs and Trope [135] used the term 'revascularization' to describe this phenomenon, there is physiological tissue formation and regeneration. It is also possible that the radiographic presentation of increased dentinal wall thickness might be due to in growth of cementum, bone, or a dentin-like material [38,139-145]. There diversity in cellular response depending on growth factors or media to where it is cultured. For e.g. DPSCs can develop odontogenic/osteogenic, chondrogenic, or adipogenic phenotypes, depending on their exposure to growth factors and morphogens [146].

CONCLUSION

The clinical success rates of endodontic treatments can exceed 80%-90%. However, many teeth are not given the opportunity to be saved by endodontic treatment and instead they are extracted, with placement of an artificial prosthesis, such as an implant. Regenerative endodontic methods have the potential for regenerating both pulp and dentin tissues and therefore may

offer an alternative method to save teeth that may have compromised structural integrity

REFERENCES

- 1) Huang GT (2008) A paradigm shift in endodontic management of immature teeth: conservation of stem cells for regeneration. *J Dent* 36, 379-386.
- 2) Reddi AH (1998) Role of morphogenetic proteins in skeletal tissue engineering and regeneration. *Nat Biotechnol* 16, 247-252.
- 3) Nakashima M, Reddi AH (2003) The application of bone morphogenetic proteins to dental tissue engineering. *Nat Biotechnol* 21, 1025-1032.
- 4) Rao MS (2004) Stem sense: a proposal for the classification of stem cells. *Stem Cells Dev* 13, 452-455.
- 5) Murray PE, Garcia-Godoy F, Hargreaves KM (2007) Regenerative endodontics: a review of current status and a call for action. *J Endod* 33, 377-390.
- 6) Menasche P (2005) The potential of embryonic stem cells to treat heart disease. *Curr Opin Mol Ther* 7, 293-299.
- 7) Gimble J, Guilak F (2003) Adipose-derived adult stem cells: isolation, characterization, and differentiation potential. *Cytotherapy* 5, 362-369.
- 8) Casagrande L, Mattuella LG, de Araujo FB, Eduardo J (2006) Stem cells in dental practice: perspectives in conservative pulp therapies. *J Clin Pediatr Dent* 31, 25-27.
- 9) Trubiani O, D'Arcangelo C, Di Iorio D, Di Nardo Di Maio F, Caputi S (2007) Dental pulp stem cells bioadhesivity: evaluation on mineral-trioxideaggregate. *Int J Immunopathol Pharmacol* 20, 81- 86.
- 10) Gronthos S, Mankani M, Brahim J, Robey PG, Shi S (2000) Postnatal human dental pulp stem cells (DPSCs) in vitro and in vivo. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 97, 13625-13630.
- 11) Miura M, Gronthos S, Zhao M, Lu B, Fisher LW, Robey PG, Shi S (2003) SHED: stem cells from human exfoliated deciduous teeth. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 100, 5807-5812.
- 12) Sonoyama W, Liu Y, Fang D, Yamaza T, Seo BM, Zhang C, Liu H, Gronthos S, Wang CY, Shi S, Wang S (2006) Mesenchymal stem cell-mediated functional tooth regeneration in swine. *PLoS One* 1, e79.
- 13) Sonoyama W, Liu Y, Yamaza T, Tuan RS, Wang S, Shi S, Huang GT (2008) Characterization of the apical papilla and its residing stem cells from human immature permanent teeth: a pilot study. *J Endod* 34, 166-171.
- 14) Seo BM, Miura M, Gronthos S, Bartold PM, Batouli S, Brahim J, Young M, Robey PG, Wang CY, Shi S (2004) Investigation of multipotent postnatal stem cells from human periodontal ligament. *Lancet* 364,149-155.
- 15) Ivanovski S, Gronthos S, Shi S, Bartold PM (2006) Stem cells in the periodontal ligament. *Oral Dis* 12, 358-363.
- 16) Gronthos S, Brahim J, Li W, Fisher LW, Cherman N, Boyde A, DenBesten P, Robey PG, Shi S (2002) Stem cell properties of human dental pulp stem cells. *J Dent Res* 81, 531-535.
- 17) Laino G, Graziano A, d'Aquino R, Pirozzi G, Lanza V, Valiante S, De Rosa A, Naro F, Vivarelli E, Papaccio G (2006) An approachable human adult stem cell source for hard-tissue engineering. *J Cell Physiol* 206, 693-701.
- 18) Papaccio G, Graziano A, d'Aquino R, Graziano MF, Pirozzi G, Menditti D, De Rosa A, Carinci F, Laino G (2006) Long-term cryopreservation of dental pulp stem cells (SBP-DPSCs) and their differentiated osteoblasts: a cell source for tissue repair. *J Cell Physiol* 208, 319-325.
- 19) Graziano A, d'Aquino R, Laino G, Proto A, Giuliano MT, Pirozzi G, De Rosa A, Di Napoli D, Papaccio G (2008) Human CD34+ stem cells produce bone nodules in vivo. *Cell Prolif* 41, 1-11.
- 20) Zhang W, Walboomers XF, Van Kuppevelt TH, Daamen WF, Van Damme PA, Bian Z, Jansen JA (2008) In vivo evaluation of human dental pulp stem cells differentiated towards multiple lineages. *J Tissue Eng Regen Med* 2, 117-125.
- 21) Batouli S, Miura M, Brahim J, Tsutsui TW, Fisher LW, Gronthos S, Robey PG, Shi S (2003) Comparison of stem cell-mediated osteogenesis and dentinogenesis. *J Dent Res* 82, 976-981.
- 22) Yu J, Deng Z, Shi J, Zhai H, Nie X, Zhuang H, Li Y, Jin Y (2006) Differentiation of dental pulp stem cells into regular shaped dentin-pulp complex induced by tooth germ cell conditioned medium. *Tissue Eng* 12, 3097-3105.
- 23) Tonomura A, Sumita Y, Ando Y, Iejima D, Kagami H, Honda MJ, Ueda M (2007) Differential inducibility of human and porcine dental pulp-derived cells into odontoblasts. *Connect Tissue Res* 48, 229-238.
- 24) D'Aquino R, De Rosa A, Laino G, Caruso F, Guida L, Rullo R, Checchi V, Laino L, Tirino V, Papaccio G (2009) Human dental pulp stem cells: from biology to clinical applications. *J Exp Zool* 312B, 408- 415.

- 25) Graziano A, d'Aquino R, Laino G, Papaccio G (2008) Dental pulp stem cells: a promising tool for bone regeneration. *Stem Cell Rev* 4, 21-26.
- 26) D'Aquino R, Graziano A, Sampaolesi M, Laino G, Pirozzi G, De Rosa A, Papaccio G (2007) Human postnatal dental pulp cells co-differentiate into osteoblasts and endotheliocytes: a pivotal synergy leading to adult bone tissue formation. *Cell Death Differ* 14, 1162-1171.
- 27) Jo YY, Lee HJ, Kook SY, Choung HW, Park JY, Chung JH, Choung YH, Kim ES, Yang HC, Choung PH (2007) Isolation and characterization of postnatal stem cells from human dental tissues. *Tissue Eng* 13, 767-773.
- 28) Zhang W, Walboomers XF, Shi S, Fan M, Jansen JA (2006) Multilineage differentiation potential of stem cells derived from human dental pulp after cryopreservation. *Tissue Eng* 12, 2813-2823.
- 29) Otaki S, Ueshima S, Shiraishi K, Sugiyama K, Hamada S, Yorimoto M, Matsuo O (2007) Mesenchymal progenitor cells in adult human dental pulp and their ability to form bone when transplanted into immunocompromised mice. *Cell Biol Int* 31, 1191-1197.
- 30) Perry BC, Zhou D, Wu X, Yang FC, Byers MA, Chu TM, Hockema JJ, Woods EJ, Goebel WS (2008) Collection, cryopreservation, and characterization of human dental pulp-derived mesenchymal stem cells for banking and clinical use. *Tissue Eng Part C Methods* 14, 149-156.
- 31) Wada N, Menicanin D, Shi S, Bartold PM, Gronthos S (2009) Immunomodulatory properties of human periodontal ligament stem cells. *J Cell Physiol* 219, 667-676.
- 32) Kitagawa M, Ueda H, Iizuka S, Sakamoto K, Oka H, Kudo Y, Ogawa I, Miyauchi M, Tahara H, Takata T (2007) Immortalization and characterization of human dental pulp cells with odontoblastic differentiation. *Arch Oral Biol* 52, 727-731.
- 33) Wang HG, Xiao MZ, Zhao SL, Hao JJ, Zhang M (2005) Immortalized human odontoblast-like cell line expressed dentin extracellular matrix in vitro. *Hua Xi Kou Qiang Yi Xue ZaZhi*. 23, 518-521. (in Chinese)
- 34) Paakkonen V, Bleicher F, Carrouel F, Vuoristo J, Salo T, Wappler I, Couble ML, Magloire H, Peters H, Tjaderhane L (2009) General expression profiles of human native odontoblasts and pulp-derived cultured odontoblast-like cells are similar but reveal differential neuropeptide expression levels. *Arch Oral Biol* 54, 55-62.
- 35) Takeda T, Tezuka Y, M. Horiuchi M, Hosono K, Iida K, Hatakeyama D, Miyaki S, Kunisada T, Shibata T, Tezuka K (2008) Characterization of dental pulp stem cells of human tooth germs. *J Dent Res* 87, 676-681.
- 36) Abe S, Yamaguchi S, Watanabe A, Hamada K, Amagasa T (2008) Hard tissue regeneration capacity of apical pulp derived cells (APDCs) from human tooth with immature apex. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 20, 90-93.
- 37) Luisi SB, Barbachan JJ, Chies JA, Filho MS (2007) Behavior of human dental pulp cells exposed to transforming growth factor-beta1 and acidic fibroblast growth factor in culture. *J Endod* 33, 833-835.
- 38) Wei X, Ling J, Wu L, Liu L, Xiao Y (2007) Expression of mineralization markers in dental pulp cells. *J Endod* 33, 703-708.
- 39) Seo BM, Sonoyama W, Yamaza T, Coppe C, Kikui T, Akiyama K, Lee JS, Shi S (2008) SHED repair critical-size calvarial defects in mice. *Oral Dis* 14, 428-434.
- 40) Cordeiro M, Dong Z, Kaneko T, Zhang Z, Miyazawa M, Shi S, Smith J, Nör J (2008) Dental pulp tissue engineering with stem cells from exfoliated deciduous teeth. *J Endod* 34, 962-969.
- 41) Nör JE (2006) Tooth regeneration in operative dentistry. *Oper Dent* 31, 633-642.
- 42) Seo B, Miura M, Gronthos S, Bartold PM, Batouli S, Brahimi J, Young M, Robey PG, Wang CY, Shi S (2004) Investigation of multipotent postnatal stem cells from human periodontal ligament. *Lancet* 364, 149-155.
- 43) Trubiani O, Di Primio R, Triani T, Pizzicannella J, Scarano A, Piattelli A, Caputi S (2005) Morphological and cytofluorometric analysis of adult mesenchymal stem cells expanded ex vivo from periodontal ligament. *Int J Immunopathol Pharmacol* 503 18, 213-221.
- 44) Shi S, Bartold PM, Miura M, Seo BM, Robey PG, Gronthos S (2005) The efficacy of mesenchymal stem cells to regenerate and repair dental structures. *Orthod Craniofac Res* 8, 191-199.
- 45) Seo B, Miura M, Sonoyama W, Coppe C, Stanyon R, Shi S (2005) Recovery of stem cells from cryopreserved periodontal ligament. *J Dent Res* 84, 907-912.
- 46) Huang GT, Sonoyama W, Liu Y, Liu H, Wang S, Shi S (2008) The hidden treasure in apical papilla: the potential

- role in pulp/dentin regeneration and bioroot engineering. *J Endod* 34, 645-651.
- 47) Trubiani O, Orsini G, Zini N, Di Iorio D, Piccirilli M, Piattelli A, Aputi S (2008) Regenerative potential of human periodontal ligament derived stem cells on three-dimensional biomaterials: a morphological report. *J Biomed Mater Res A* 87, 986-993.
 - 48) Li Y, Jin F, Du Y, Ma Z, Li F, Wu G, Shi J, Zhu X, Yu J, Jin Y (2008) Cementum and periodontal ligament-like tissue formation induced using bioengineered dentin. *Tissue Eng Part A* 14, 1731-1742.
 - 49) Nakashima M (1991) Establishment of primary cultures of pulp cells from bovine permanent incisors. *Arch Oral Biol* 36, 655-663.
 - 50) Tsukamoto Y, Fukutani S, Shin-Ike T, Kubota T, Sato S, Suzuki Y, Mori M (1992) Mineralized nodule formation by cultures of human dental pulp-derived fibroblasts. *Arch Oral Biol* 37, 1045-1055.
 - 51) About I, Bottero MJ, de Denato P, Camps J, Franquin JC, Mitsiadis TA (2000) Human dentin production in vitro. *Exp Cell Res* 258, 33-41.
 - 52) Couble ML, Farges JC, Bleicher F, Perrat-Mabillon B, Boudeulle M, Magloire H (2000) Odontoblast differentiation of human dental pulp cells in explant cultures. *Calcif Tissue Int* 66, 129-138.
 - 53) Saito T, Ogawa M, Hata Y, Bessho K (2004) Acceleration effect of human recombinant bone morphogenetic protein-2 on differentiation of human pulp cells into odontoblasts. *J Endod* 30, 205-208.
 - 54) Huang GT, Sonoyama W, Chen J, Park SH (2006) In vitro characterization of human dental pulp cells: various isolation methods and culturing environments. *Cell Tissue Res* 324, 225-236.
 - 55) Song L, Tuan RS (2004) Transdifferentiation potential of human mesenchymal stem cells derived from bone marrow. *Faseb J* 18, 980-982.
 - 56) Smith AJ, Tobias RS, Cassidy N, Bégue-Kirn C, Ruch JV, Lesot H (1995) Influence of substrate nature and immobilization of implanted dentin matrix components during induction of reparative dentinogenesis. *Connect Tissue Res* 32, 291-295.
 - 57) Veis A (1985) Chemistry and biology of mineralized tissues. Butler WT ed, EBSCO Media, Birmingham, 170-184.
 - 58) Srinivasan R, Chen B, Gorski JP, George A (1999) Recombinant expression and characterization of dentin matrix protein 1. *Connect Tissue Res* 40, 251-258.
 - 59) Feng JQ, Luan X, Wallace J, Jing D, Ohshima T, Kulkarni AB, D'Souza RN, Kozak CA, MacDougall M (1998) Genomic organization, chromosomal mapping, and promoter analysis of the mouse dentin sialophosphoprotein (Dspp) gene, which codes for both dentin sialoprotein and dentin phosphoprotein. *J Biol Chem* 273, 9457-9464.
 - 60) MacDougall M, Simmons D, Luan X, Gu TT, DuPont BR (1997) Assignment of dentin sialophosphoprotein (DSPP) to the critical DG12 locus on human chromosome 4 band q21.3 by in situ hybridization. *Cytogenet Cell Genet* 79, 121-122.
 - 61) Hao J, Narayanan K, Ramachandran A, He G, Almushayt A, Evans C, George A (2002) Odontoblast cells immortalized by telomerase produce mineralized dentin-like tissue both in vitro and in vivo. *J Biol Chem* 277, 19976-19981.
 - 62) He G, Dahl T, Veis A, George A (2003) Dentin matrix protein 1 initiates hydroxyapatite formation in vitro. *Connect Tissue Res* 44, Suppl 1, 240-245.
 - 63) Narayanan K, Ramachandran A, Hao J, He G, Park KW, Cho M, George A (2003) Dual function roles of dentin matrix protein 1. *J Biol Chem* 278, 17500-17508.
 - 64) He G, George A (2004) Dentin matrix protein 1 immobilized on type I collagen fibrils facilitates apatite deposition in vitro. *J Biol Chem* 279, 11649-11656.
 - 65) Almushayt A, Narayanan K, Zaki A, George A (2006) Dentin matrix protein 1 induces cytodifferentiation of dental pulp stem cells into odontoblasts. *Gene Ther* 13, 611-620.
 - 66) Prescott R, Alsanea R, Fayad M, Johnson B, Wenckus C, Hao J, John AS, George A (2008) In vivo generation of dental pulp-like tissue by using dental pulp stem cells, a collagen scaffold, and dentin matrix protein 1 after subcutaneous transplantation in mice. *J Endod* 34, 421-426.
 - 67) Qin C, Brunn JC, Cadena E, Ridall A, Butler WT (2003) Dentin sialoprotein in bone and dentin sialophosphoprotein gene expressed by osteoblasts. *Connect Tissue Res* 44, Suppl 1, 179-183. 504

- 68) Baba O, Qin C, Brunn JC, Jones JE, Wygant JN, McIntyre BW, Butler WT (2004) Detection of dentin sialoprotein in rat periodontium. *Eur J Oral Sci* 112, 163-170.
- 69) Nomiya K, Kitamura C, Tsujisawa T, Nagayoshi M, Morotomi T, Terashita M, Nishihara T (2007) Effects of lipopolysaccharide on newly established rat dental pulp-derived cell line with odontoblastic properties. *J Endod* 33, 1187-1191.
- 70) Kasugai S, Adachi M, Ogura H (1988) Establishment and characterization of a clonal cell line (RPC2A) from dental pulp of the rat incisor. *Arch Oral Biol* 33, 887-891.
- 71) Sun ZL, Fang DN, Wu XY, Ritchie HH, Bègue-Kirn C, Wataha JC, Hanks CT, Butler WT (1988) Expression of dentin sialoprotein (DSP) and other molecular determinants by a new cell line from dental papillae, MDPC-23. *Connect Tissue Res* 37, 251-261.
- 72) Arany S, Nakata A, Kameda T, Koyota S, Ueno Y, Sugiyama T (2006) Phenotype properties of a novel spontaneously immortalized odontoblast-lineage cell line. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 342, 718-724.
- 73) Ritchie HH, Liu J, Kasugai S, Moller P (2002) A mineralizing rat dental pulp cell subline expressing collagen type I and dentin sialoprotein phosphorin transcripts. *In Vitro Cell Dev Biol Anim* 38, 25-29.
- 74) MacDougall M, Thiemann F, Ta H, Hsu P, Chen LS, Snead ML (1995) Temperature sensitive simian virus 40 large T antigen immortalization of murine odontoblast cell cultures: establishment of clonal odontoblast cell line. *Connect Tissue Res* 33, 97-103.
- 75) Giannobile WV (1996) Periodontal tissue engineering by growth factors. *Bone* 19, Suppl, 23s-37s.
- 76) Nakao K, Itoh M, Tomita Y, Tomooka Y, Tsuji T (2004) FGF-2 potently induces both proliferation and DSP expression in collagen type I gel cultures of adult incisor immature pulp cells. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun* 325, 1052-1059.
- 77) Ferrara N, Gerber HP, LeCouter J (2003) The biology of VEGF and its receptors. *Nat Med* 9, 669-676.
- 78) Roy H, Bhardwaj S, Ylä-Herttua S (2006) Biology of vascular endothelial growth factors. *FEBS Lett* 580, 2879-2887.
- 79) Tai TF, Chan CP, Lin CC, Chen LI, Jeng JH, Chang MC (2008) Transforming growth factor beta2 regulates growth and differentiation of pulp cells via ALK5/Smad2/3. *J Endod* 34, 427-432.
- 80) Nie X, Jin Y, Zhang CY (2004) Induction of transforming growth factor-beta 1 and dentin noncollagen proteins on tissue engineering pulp. *Zhongguo Xue Fu Chong Jian Wai Ke Za Zhi* 18, 115-118. (in Chinese)
- 81) Aberg T, Wozney J, Thesleff I (1997) Expression patterns of bone morphogenetic proteins (Bmps) in the developing mouse tooth suggest roles in morphogenesis and cell differentiation. *Dev Dyn* 210, 383-396.
- 82) Nagatomo KJ, Tompkins KA, Fong H, Zhang H, Foster BL, Chu EY, Murakami A, Stadmeier L, Canalis E, Somerman MJ (2008) Transgenic overexpression of gremlin results in developmental defects in enamel and dentin in mice. *Connect Tissue Res* 49, 391-400.
- 83) Ripamonti U, Reddi AH (1997) Tissue engineering, morphogenesis, and regeneration of the periodontal tissues by bone morphogenetic proteins. *Crit Rev Oral Biol Med* 8, 154-163.
- 84) Urist MR (1965) Bone: formation by auto induction. *Science* 150, 893-899.
- 85) Miyazono K (2000) Positive and negative regulation of TGF-beta signaling. *J Cell Sci* 113, 1101-1109.
- 86) Nakashima M (2005) Bone morphogenetic proteins in dentin regeneration for potential use in endodontic therapy. *Cytokine Growth Factor Rev* 16, 369-376.
- 87) Nakashima M (1994) Induction of dentin formation on canine amputated pulp by recombinant human bone morphogenetic proteins (BMP)-2 and -4. *J Dent Res* 73, 1515-1522.
- 88) Nakashima M (1994) Induction of dentine in amputated pulp of dogs by recombinant human bone morphogenetic proteins-2 and -4 with collagen matrix. *Arch Oral Biol* 39, 1085-1089.
- 89) Jepsen S, Albers HK, Fleiner B, Tucker M, Rueger D (1997) Recombinant human osteogenic protein-1 induces dentin formation: an experimental study in miniature swine. *J Endod* 23, 378-382.
- 90) Ren WH, Yang LJ, Dong SZ (1999) Induction of reparative dentin formation in dogs with combined recombinant human bone morphogenetic protein 2 and fibrin sealant. *Chin J Dent Res* 2, 21-24.

- 91) Lovschall H, Fejerskov O, Flyvbjerg A (2001) Pulp capping with recombinant human insulin-like growth factor I (rhIGF-I) in rat molars. *Adv Dent Res* 15, 108-112.
- 92) Nakashima M, Iohara K, Zheng L (2006) Gene therapy for dentin regeneration with bone morphogenetic proteins. *Curr Gene Ther* 6, 551-560. 505
- 93) Nakashima M, Nagasawa H, Yamada Y, Reddi AH (1994) Regulatory role of transforming growth factor-beta, bone morphogenetic protein-2, and protein-4 on gene expression of extracellular matrix proteins and differentiation of dental pulp cells. *Dev Biol* 162, 18-28.
- 94) Iohara K, Nakashima M, Ito M, Ishikawa M, Nakasima A, Akamine A (2004) Dentin regeneration by dental pulp stem cell therapy with recombinant human bone morphogenetic protein 2. *J Dent Res* 83, 590-595.
- 95) Yang X, Walboomers XF, van den Beucken JJ, Bian Z, Fan M, Jansen JA (2009) Hard tissue formation of STRO-1-selected rat dental pulp stem cells in vivo. *Tissue Eng Part A* 15, 367-375.
- 96) Goldberg M, Six N, Decup F, Bourd K, Palmier K, Salih E, Veis A, Lasfargues JJ (2002) Mineralization of the dental pulp: contributions of tissue engineering to tomorrow's therapeutics in odontology. *Pathol Biol (Paris)* 50, 194-203. (in French)
- 97) Decup F, Six N, Palmier B, Buch D, Lasfargues JJ, Salih E, Goldberg M (2000) Bone sialoprotein-induced reparative dentinogenesis in the pulp of rat's molar. *Clin Oral Investig* 4, 110-119.
- 98) Goldberg M, Six N, Decup F, Buch D, Soheili Majd E, Lasfargues JJ, Salih E, Stanislawski L (2001) Application of bioactive molecules in pulp-capping situations. *Adv Dent Res* 15, 91-95.
- 99) Rutherford RB, Wahle J, Tucker M, Rueger D, Charette M (1993) Induction of reparative dentine formation in monkeys by recombinant human osteogenic protein-1. *Arch Oral Biol* 38, 571-576.
- 100) Rutherford RB, Spångberg L, Tucker M, Rueger D, Charette M (1994) The time-course of the induction of reparative dentine formation in monkeys by recombinant human osteogenic protein-1. *Arch Oral Biol* 39, 833-838.
- 101) Rutherford RB, Gu K (2000) Treatment of inflamed ferret dental pulps with recombinant bone morphogenetic protein-7. *Eur J Oral Sci* 108, 202-206.
- 102) Six N, Lasfargues JJ, Goldberg M (2002) Differential repair responses in the coronal and radicular areas of the exposed rat molar pulp induced by recombinant human bone morphogenetic protein 7 (osteogenic protein 1). *Arch Oral Biol* 47, 177-187.
- 103) Sloan AJ, Rutherford RB, Smith AJ (2000) Stimulation of the rat dentine-pulp complex by bone morphogenetic protein-7 in vitro. *Arch Oral Biol* 45, 173-177.
- 104) Lin ZM, Qin W, Zhang N, Xiao L, Ling J (2007) Adenovirus-mediated recombinant human bone morphogenetic protein-7 expression promotes differentiation of human dental pulp cells. *J Endod* 33, 930-935.
- 105) Hosoya A, Kim JY, Cho SW, Jung HS (2008) BMP4 signaling regulates formation of Hertwig's epithelial root sheath during tooth root development. *Cell Tissue Res* 333, 503-509.
- 106) Bouhadir KH, Mooney DJ (1998) In vitro and in vivo models for the reconstruction of intercellular signaling. *Ann N Y Acad Sci* 842, 188-194.
- 107) Bi Y, Ehrlichou D, Kiltz TM, Inkson CA, Embree MC, Sonoyama W, Li L, Leet AI, Seo BM, Zhang L, Shi S, Young MF (2007) Identification of tendon stem/progenitor cells and the role of the extracellular matrix in their niche. *Nat Med* 13, 1219-1227.
- 108) Yamamura T (1985) Differentiation of pulpal cells and inductive influences of various matrices with reference to pulpal wound healing. *J Dent Res* 64, 530-540.
- 109) Vacatello M, D'Auria G, Falcigno L, Dettin M, Gambaretto R, Di Bello C, Paolillo L (2005) Conformational analysis of heparin binding peptides. *Biomaterials* 26, 3207-3214.
- 110) Yamada Y, Ueda M, Naiki T, Takahashi M, Hata K, Nagasaka T (2004) Autogenous injectable bone for regeneration with mesenchymal stem cells and platelet-rich plasma: tissue engineered bone regeneration. *Tissue Eng* 10, 955-964.
- 111) Young CS, Terada S, Vacanti JP, Honda M, Bartlett JD, Yelick PC (2002) Tissue engineering of complex tooth structures on biodegradable polymer scaffolds. *J Dent Res* 81, 695-700.
- 112) Sharma B, Elisseff JH (2004) Engineering structurally organized cartilage and bone tissues. *Ann Biomed Eng* 32, 148-159.

- 113) Feng Z, Yamato M, Akutsu T, Nakamura T, Okano T, Umezumi M (2003) Investigation on the mechanical properties of contracted collagen gels as a scaffold for tissue engineering. *Artif Organs* 27, 84-91.
- 114) Thibodeau B, Teixeira F, Yamauchi M, Caplan DJ, Trope M (2007) Pulp revascularization of immature dog teeth with apical periodontitis. *J Endod* 33, 680-689.
- 115) Lee KY, Mooney DJ (2001) Hydrogels for tissue engineering. *Chem Rev* 101, 1869-1879.
- 116) Chan CP, Lan WH, Chang MC, Chen YJ, Lan WC, Chang HH, Jeng JH (2005) Effects of TGF- β s on the growth, collagen synthesis and collagen lattice contraction of human dental pulp fibroblasts in vitro. *Arch Oral Biol* 50(506), 469-479.
- 117) Burdick JA, Anseth KS (2002) Photoencapsulation of osteoblasts in injectable RGD-modified PEG hydrogels for bone tissue engineering. *Biomaterials* 23, 4315-4323.
- 118) Jadowiec JA, Celil AB, Hollinger JO (2003) Bone tissue engineering: recent advances and promising therapeutic agents. *Expert Opin Biol Ther* 3, 409-423.
- 119) Guo HY, Wu BL, Guo XM, Yang C, Xu P, Wang CY (2005) Reconstruction of dentin-pulp complex structure by tissue engineering technology. *Zhonghua Kou Qiang Yi Xue Za Zhi* 40, 511-514. (in Chinese)
- 120) Wang FM, Qiu K, Hu T, Wan CX, Zhou XD, Gutmann JL (2006) Biodegradable porous calcium polyphosphate scaffolds for the three-dimensional culture of dental pulp cells. *Int Endod J* 39, 477-483.
- 121) Graziano A, d'Aquino R, Cusella-De Angelis MG, Laino G, Piattelli A, Pacifici M, De Rosa A, Papaccio G (2007) Concave pit-containing scaffold surfaces improve stem cell-derived osteoblast performance and lead to significant bone tissue formation. *PloS One* 2, e496.
- 122) Graziano A, d'Aquino R, Cusella-De Angelis MG, De Francesco F, Giordano A, Laino G, Piattelli A, Traini T, De Rosa A, Papaccio G (2008) Scaffold's surface geometry significantly affects human stem cell bone tissue engineering. *J Cell Physiol* 214, 166-172.
- 123) Mooney DJ, Powell C, Piana J, Rutherford B (1996) Engineering dental pulp-like tissue in vitro. *Biotechnol Prog* 12, 865-868.
- 124) Bohl KS, Shon J, Rutherford B, Mooney DJ (1998) Role of synthetic extracellular matrix in development of engineered dental pulp. *J Biomater Sci Polym Ed* 9, 749-764.
- 125) Buurma B, Gu K, Rutherford RB (1999) Transplantation of human pulpal and gingival fibroblasts attached to synthetic scaffolds. *Eur J Oral Sci* 107, 282-289.
- 126) Kuo TF, Huang AT, Chang HH, Lin FH, Chen ST, Chen RS, Chou CH, Lin HC, Chiang H, Chen MH (2008) Regeneration of dentin-pulp complex with cementum and periodontal ligament formation using dental bud cells in gelatin-chondroitin-hyaluronan tripolymer scaffold in swine. *J Biomed Mater Res A* 86, 1062-1068.
- 127) Gotlieb EL, Murray PE, Namerow KN, Kuttler S, Garcia-Godoy F (2008) An ultrastructural investigation of tissue-engineered pulp constructs implanted within endodontically treated teeth. *J Am Dent Assoc* 139, 457-465.
- 128) Bishop BG, Woollard GW (2002) Modern endodontic therapy for an incompletely developed tooth. *Gen Den* 50, 252-256.
- 129) Thibodeau B, Trope M (2007) Pulp revascularization of a necrotic infected immature permanent tooth: case report and review of the literature. *Pediatr Dent* 29, 47-50.
- 130) Cotti E, Mereu M, Lusso D (2008) Regenerative treatment of an immature, traumatized tooth with apical periodontitis. *J Endod* 34, 611-616.
- 131) Shah N, Logani A, Bhaskar U, Aggarwal V (2008) Efficacy of revascularization to induce apexification/apexogenesis in infected, nonvital, immature teeth: a pilot clinical study. *J Endod* 34, 919-925.
- 132) Jung IY, Lee SJ, Hargreaves KM (2008) Biologically based treatment of immature permanent teeth with pulpal necrosis: a case series. *J Endod* 34, 876-887.
- 133) Reynolds K, Johnson JD, Cohenca N (2009) Pulp revascularization of necrotic bilateral bicuspid using a modified novel technique to eliminate potential coronal discoloration: a case report. *Int Endod J* 42, 84-92.
- 134) Chueh LH, Huang GT (2006) Immature teeth with periradicular periodontitis or abscess undergoing apexogenesis: a paradigm shift. *J Endod* 32, 1205-1213.
- 135) Banchs F, Trope M (2004) Revascularization of immature permanent teeth with apical periodontitis: new treatment protocol? *J Endod* 30, 196-200.

- 136) Rule DC, Winter GB (1966) Root growth and apical repair subsequent to pulpal necrosis in children. *Br Dent J* 120, 586-590.
- 137) Iwaya S, Ikawa M, Kubota M (2001) Revascularization of an immature permanent tooth with apical periodontitis and sinus tract. *Dent Traumatol* 17, 185-187.
- 138) Weisleder R, Benitez CR (2003) Maturogenesis: is it a new concept? *J Endod* 29, 776-778.
- 139) Østby BN (1961) The role of the blood clot in endodontic therapy: an experimental histologic study. *Acta Odontol Scand* 19, 324-353.
- 140) Nevins AJ, Finkelstein F, Borden BG, Laporta R (1976) Revitalization of pulpless open apex teeth in rhesus monkeys, using collagen-calcium phosphate gel. *J Endod* 2, 159-165.
- 141) Ritter AL, Ritter AV, Murrah V, Sigurdsson A, Trope M (2004) Pulp revascularization of replanted immature dog teeth after treatment with minocycline and doxycycline assessed by laser Doppler flowmetry, radiography, and histology. *Dent Traumatol* 20, 75-84.
- 142) Nevins AJ, Finkelstein F, Laporta R, Borden BG (1978) Induction of hard tissue into pulpless open apex teeth using collagen-calcium phosphate gel. *J Endod* 4, 76-81.
- 143) Skoglund A, Tronstad L (1981) Pulpal changes in replanted and autotransplanted immature teeth of dogs. *J Endod* 7, 309-316.
- 144) Sheppard PR, Burich RL (1980) Effects of extraoral exposure and multiple avulsions on revascularization of reimplanted teeth in dogs. *J Dent Res* 59, 140. (Abstract)
- 145) Kvinnsland I, Heyeraas KJ (1989) Dentin and osteodentin matrix formation in apicoectomized replanted incisors in cats. *Acta Odontol Scand* 47, 41-52.
- 146) Huang GT, Shagranova K, Chan SW (2006) Formation of odontoblast-like cells from cultured human dental pulp cells on dentin in vitro. *J Endod* 32, 1066-1073.